

Motivation Behind Digital Banking Adoption: An Empherical Analysis

Mr.Satheesh S, Mr. Sanjay J

III B. (CS) Rathinam College of Arts and Sciences, Coimbatore

ABSTRACT: The banking industry is in utmost development. The emergence of internet and its widespread patronage provides an opportunity for modern transition in the banking industry. This in turn has an impact on transfer of Traditional banking towards Digital banking. The objective of the study is to analyse the factors influencing the banking customers towards digital banking adoption and determine the services that are attracted by banking customers. Primary data were collected from 68 respondents using structured questionnaire and the respondents were the banking customers of Coimbatore city. Non-Probability sampling method namely convenience sampling technique was adopted to select the sample respondents. Accordingly the collected data were analysed using discriptive statistics and ranking technique. The result of the study reveals the convenience factor influences the most and also the service of easy fund transfer attracts the banking customer to adopt digital banking.

KEY WORDS: Digital Banking, Internet Banking, Banking Customers, Digital Banking Adoption, Convenience Factor, Easy Fund Transfer, Customer Preference, Banking Services

I. Introduction:

Digital banking is the process of performing banking activities through internet and it's also called as internet or electronic banking. Though it has been emerged in 90th century but its growth has been speeded up in the mid of 20th century . In India, digital banking and its importance arises after the development of android mobiles and covid . The number of digital banking users raises day by day dramatically. Not only digital banking customers are raising ,its various services and features are up-to-date as per the needs of costumer and the apps developed by the banks are also user friendly now-a-days. Though various changes has been taken place but it can't so be implemented in rural areas as same as in cities . Thus customer's awarness which is defined as customer's knowledge which is more important for digital banking development. By the development of new technologies various online services are provided by banks through its self developed applications. The various services enabled by banks in online are mobile banking , user friendly application, security, 24 hour accessibility and these factors promote digital

II. Scope of the Study

The main goal of the study is to define which factor influences the most of the people to move on digital banking. The various services which are provided by the the banks and also attracts the customer to be use digital banking.

Objectives of the Study:

The objective of the study are

1. To identify factors motivating digital banking adoption .
2. To find out most preferred mode of digital banking services among the customer.

III. Review of the Literature

Mohan et.al (2021),The customers prefer digital banking rather than to visit the bank. And they believe that online banking are much more easier than offline banking. Jain et.al (2020),The emergence of digital banking landscape in India which are lying ahead, which need to be tackled so that the nation can go ahead in the path of becoming digital economy. Maitlo et.al (2015), The factors like convenience, security perception ,perceived risk and prior knowledge about the online banking which have impact adoption of online banking.

IV. Reseach Methodology

The study was carried out in Coimbatore city. It is the second largest city in Tamilnadu and 16th largest district in India. The literacy rate and earning capacity of the citizens are comparatively higher than other districts of Tamilnadu. Covenience sampling was used to select the samplingrespondents. The sample is drawn with banking customers residing Coimbatore city and,with the sample size of 68 respondents . The sampling is specifically drawn from the banking customers residing in coimbatore city. The study was mainly based on primary data. Primary data was collected using standard questionnaire. The tool of descriptive statistics and ranking techniques was used.

V. Analysis And Discussion:

Profile of the Respondents

Socio economic profile of the respondents is more important for a successful study. The socio economic variables collected for the study are gender, age, education and occupation which will be more helpful for data analysis.

Table 1

Demographic Variables	Categories	Frequencies	Percentage
Gender	Male	18	26.5
	Female	50	73.5
	Total	68	100
Age (In Years)	Below 20	13	19.1
	21 – 35	49	72.1
	35 – 50	6	8.8
	Above 50	-	-
	Total	68	100
Education	High School	13	19.1
	Under Graduate	24	36
	Post Graduate	25	37
	Diploma	2	3.2
	Professional Degree	4	4.7
	Total	68	100
Occupation	Students	45	68.7
	Employed	15	22.1
	Business Man	8	9.1

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Occupation	Business Man	8	9.1
	Total	68	100
Monthly Income	Below 20000	10	14.4
Monthly Income	21000-40000	7	10.3
Monthly Income	41000-60000	10	14.4
Monthly Income	Above 60000	10	14.4
Monthly Income	None of the Above	31	45.6
Monthly Income	Total	68	100

Socio economic factor of the respondents

Table 1 deals with Socio economic profile of the respondents has great significance towards framing successful market strategies for any banking institutions. Therefore the banking institution pay due concern towards analyzing those aspects , as its implication are greater and worth considering. On the basis of age, most of the respondents belongs to the age group of 20-35 years(71.6%),female respondents contributes the most(73.1),90.9percent of the respondents where students so they don't have proper earnings. On the basis of data collected most of the user prefer online banking due to easy accessibility and fund transfer and mainly because of convenience.

A. Services Influencing Respondents Towards Digital Banking Adoption:

Once the services are satisfied by the customer it makes them to use again and again. The various services which makes customer to be more adopted are such as easy fund transfer, easy loan availing and repayment, e-passbook, balance enquiry, bill payments and all other payments.

SERVICES	FREQUENCIES	PERCENTAGE	RANK
Easy Fund Transfer	30	42.9	1
Balance Enquiry	10	15.8	3
Bill Payments	12	17.7	2
Easy Loan	3	4.4	6
Deposits	8	11.9	4
Cards	1	1.5	7
Insurance	4	5.9	5
Total	68	100	

Service's influencing the respondent's towards digital banking adoption

Among various services offered by the banks in its application and the most attracted services by the is easy fund transfer. Among 68 respondent's 30 of them is attracted and enjoyed by customer is easy fund transfer of (42.9%) which ranks first, bill payments about (17.7%) which ranks second, balance enquiry is attracted by (15.8%) which ranks third , deposits about (11.9%) which ranks fourth ,insurance about (5.9%) which ranks fifth, easy loan about(4.4%) which ranks sixth and cards about (1.5%) which ranks seventh

.Thus fund transfer is an important work in all organization and it is more easier by digital banking adoption which is given in the table 2.

B. Factors Influencing Respondents Towards Digital Banking Adoption:

In order to have a thorough knowledge about the dominant factors influencing the respondents towards the usage of digital banking through online platforms, respondents intention to use digital banking was defined using the sampling. Various factors has been defined and which influences the most is discussed below under ranking technique.

Table 3

FACTORS	FREQUENCIES	PERCENTAGE	RANK
Convenience	28	41.2	1
24*7 Accessibility	9	14.3	2
Safety	4	5.9	7
Quick Transaction	8	11.9	3
Remote Access	5	7.4	6
Cashless Transaction	6	8.9	5
Time Savings	7	10.4	4
Total	68	100	

Factor's influencing the respondent's towards digital banking adoption.

On the basis of analysis, the factors influencing the banking customer to move on digital banking adoption has greater impact on easy fund transfer of (41.2%) which ranks first among all other factors. Which is followed by 24*7 accessibility about (14.3%) ranks second, quick transaction is about (11.9%) ranks third, Time savings about(10.4%) which ranks forth, cashless transaction is about (8.9%) which ranks fifth, remote access is about(7.4%) which ranks sixth, and safety ranks seventh with (5.9%) which is give in table 3.

A. Findings Of The Study:

1. The findings of the study are

- Easy Fund Transfer is the most preferred service among the respondents of the analysis.

- Convenience is the most preferred factor among the various factors that are enlisted in this study.

VI. Conclusion

Customers use digital banking because they are influenced by the factors and also the services provided by the banks in the digital banking. Easy fund transfer is the most attracted services among the 68 respondents. Fund transfer through digital banking is very quick, it saves time and money of the use. The banks also develop user friendly application in order to attract large number of the customer. Convenience is the most important factor which influences the customer to use digital banking often.

References

1. Yiu, C. S., Grant, K., & Edgar, D. (2007). Factors affecting the adoption of Internet Banking in Hong Kong—implications for the banking sector. *International journal of information management*, 27(5), 336-
2. Grabner-Kräuter, S., & Breitenecker, R. J. (2011). Factors influencing online banking adoption: evidence from the Austrian market. *International Journal of Internet Marketing and Advertising*, 6(4), 333-
3. Shaikh, F. M., Kazi, Z. H., & Khaskheley, A. (2014). Factors that influence the adoption of online banking services in Hyderabad. *Romanian Statistical Review Supplement*, 62(11), 49-
4. Hough, J. A. C. Q. U. E. S., & Chan, K. Y. (2018, April). Factors influencing the acceptance of digital banking: An empirical study in South Africa based on the enhanced Technology Acceptance Model. In *Proceedings of the 27th Annual Conference of the International Association for Management of Technology (IAMOT 2018)*, Birmingham, UK (pp. 22-26).
5. Jain, V., Sharma, M. P., Kumar, A., & Kansal, A. (2020). Digital Banking: A Case Study of India. *Solid State Technology*, 63(6), 19980-19988.
6. Srouji, J. (2020). Digital payments, the cashless economy, and financial inclusion in the United Arab Emirates: Why is everyone still transacting in cash?. *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*, 13(11),
7. Koroleva, E.V., Kudryavtseva, T. (2020). Factors Influencing Digital Bank Performance. In: Antipova, T., Rocha, Á. (eds) *Digital Science 2019. DSIC 2019. Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing*, vol 1114.
8. Springer, Cham.
9. Mohan, M. M., Kumar, T. H., & Rao, P. N. (2021). Factors Influencing Customers To Use Digital Banking Services In Twin Cities Of Telangana State. *NVEO-NATURAL VOLATILES & ESSENTIAL OILS Journal| NVEO*, 10560-10573.